

A New Complex of Palladium (II) with N-Amidino-S-Ethylthiourea

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A new palladium complex of composition, Pd (HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂, has been prepared and its structure is discussed. The formation of a new variety of palladium ethyl mercaptide, orange-yellow in color and insoluble in benzene, is reported.

1-Amidino-2-thiourea behaves as a bidentate ligand and can react in either of its tautomeric forms I and II to give inner metallic complexes with a number of transition metal ions^{1,2}.

Ray and co-workers^{1,2} have suggested that it reacts with Cu(II) and Pd(II) in the thiol-form II to form six-membered chelate ring structure involving bonding through nitrogen and sulfur, while it shows the reaction of the thiol-form I to produce the nickel complex in which the six-membered chelate ring is formed by bonding through two nitrogen atoms. The presence of metal-sulfur linkage in Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes is also indicated by their infrared spectra³. Recent studies have shown that N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea (HASETU) derived from 1-amidino-2-thiourea by replacing the hydrogen atom of its thiol group (form II) with —C₂H₅ reacts with Cu(II) to form a chelate complex with six-membered ring structure in which the bonding occurs through nitrogen atoms^{4,5}. Considering that palladium (II) has great affinity for sulfur donor atom, it is of interest to prepare palladium complex of HASETU and to study its properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and the preparation of HASETU-HBr are described in earlier papers^{4,5}. Palladium chloride used was of A.R. grade. K₂PdCl₄ was prepared by following the procedure reported in the literature⁶. Other reagents and solvents employed were of A. R. quality.

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Preparation of Palladium Complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea: Pd(HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂. 1.34 g. of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea hydrobromide(HASETU.HBr) in 50 ml. of cold (5°) aqueous solution of pH 7.5 was added to a cold solution of 0.92 g. of K₂PdCl₄ in 50 ml of water (pH 3.5). The orange colored precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, alcohol, benzene and ether, dried over P₂O₅ under vacuum to a constant weight and analyzed for Pd, N, S, Cl, C and H. The deuterated palladium complex was prepared by adding a solution of deuterated reagent in D₂O to a solution of K₂PdCl₄ in D₂O. The solid complex was washed with D₂O and dried at 105°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of chemical analysis suggest that the orange compound formed by the reaction of K₂PdCl₄ with HASETU.HBr may be represented by the formula, Pd(HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂ (Found % of Pd—29.20, N—15.07, S—8.47, Cl—19.50, C—14.00 and H—3.80. Required for Pd(HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂, % of Pd—29.60, N—15.59, S—8.92, Cl—19.72, C—13.40 and H—3.70). It is diamagnetic and insoluble in cold water. It produces with hot water an orange-colored colloidal solution which gives test for chloride. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, pyridine and acetone, and practically insoluble in benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, etc. It does not show any loss in weight on heating up to 160° and decomposes above 160°. This observation seems to suggest that H₂O molecules are most probably coordinated to Pd.

When an aqueous solution of HASETU.HBr is added to a solution (pH 1.5—4) of PdCl₂ in HCl, a mixture of Pd(HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂ and yellow colored palladium ethyl mercaptide is produced. The repeated washing of the mixture with benzene removes palladium ethyl mercaptide leaving the pure compound, Pd (HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂.

The addition of an aqueous solution of HASETU.HBr to a solution of K₂PdCl₄ at pH 12 leads to the formation of an orange-yellow solid substance which is partly soluble in benzene. The benzene soluble portion is found to be the yellow-colored palladium ethyl mercaptide described earlier. Chemical analysis data of the benzene insoluble orange-yellow residue correspond to those of yellow palladium ethyl mercaptide.

TABLE I
Chemical Analysis and Solubility Data of Palladium Ethyl Mercaptides

	Pd %	S %	Solubility in benzene at 30° × 10 ³ (g/litre)
Benzene soluble solid (yellow)	46.20	27.80	770
Benzene insoluble solid (orange-yellow)	45.80	27.90	9
Required for Pd(SC ₂ H ₅) ₂	46.52	28.02	—

The two varieties of palladium ethyl mercaptide are also formed by the treatment of Pd(HASETU)(H₂O)₂Cl₂ with 2.5N NaOH. The infrared spectra of the two varieties of palladium ethyl mercaptide are similar except that the orange-yellow variety shows two additional weak bands at 3056 cm⁻¹ and 3096 cm⁻¹ and its peak at 2985 cm⁻¹ is observed near

3050 cm^{-1} in the yellow variety. Further, the peaks at 1650 cm^{-1} in orange-yellow (insoluble) variety is less intense than that of the soluble variety. It is quite possible that the benzene insoluble palladium ethyl mercaptide has a polymeric structure as shown below

which is similar to that of $(\text{PdCl}_2)_n$.

The infrared spectra of $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and of its deuterated form are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The important features of the spectrum of $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$ are a

Fig. 1 : IR Absorption Spectra of Palladium(II) Complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea in KBr pellets.

strong band at 3420 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 3360 cm^{-1} . These bands are observed at 2570 cm^{-1} and 2480 cm^{-1} in the deuterated complex. Considering that the NH stretching frequencies appear in this region, they are tentatively assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of NH_2 . Their appearance at frequencies much lower than those observed⁵ in $\text{Co}(\text{ASETU})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{ASETU})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ASETU})_2$ may possibly be due to coordination of free NH_2 group to palladium atom. Two strong bands occur at 3310 cm^{-1} and 1665 cm^{-1} which are missing in the spectra of HASETU-HBr and of its Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes⁵. Sartori *et al.* have reported that the stretching frequency of coordinated H_2O is lowered by 300-400 cm^{-1} and the bending of the same is raised by some tens of cm^{-1} from the fundamental frequencies ($\nu_1 = 3652 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2 = 1595 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu_3 = 3750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

of free H_2O ⁷. It is, therefore, reasonable to attribute the observed bands at 3310 cm^{-1} and 1665 cm^{-1} to coordinated H_2O . Evidence in support of the assignment is provided by the disappearance of these bands on deuteration and appearance of new bands at 2420 cm^{-1} and 1355 cm^{-1} . It may be mentioned that the effect of heat on $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$ reported earlier also supports the presence of coordinated H_2O .

Fig. 2 : IR Absorption Spectra of Palladium(II) Complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea in KBr pellets.
 1. Undeuterated $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$.
 2. Deuterated $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$.

The C—S stretching vibration, which is assigned to the band near $673\text{--}680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{HASETU}\cdot\text{HBr}$, $\text{Co}(\text{ASETU})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{ASETU})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ASETU})_2$ ⁵, appears to occur at 588 cm^{-1} in $\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$. The large shift of the C—S band from 673 cm^{-1} in $\text{HASETU}\cdot\text{HBr}$ to 588 cm^{-1} in the palladium complex may be interpreted to mean that the complex contains the linkage $\text{Pd}\leftarrow\text{S}$. As expected, the peak at 588 cm^{-1} remains unaltered on deuteration. The formation of palladium ethyl mercaptan by the action of alkali on $[\text{Pd}(\text{HASETU})((\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2)]$ also leads to the conclusion that the linkage $\text{Pd}\leftarrow\text{S}$ is present in the palladium complex. It is, however, possible that the band at 588 cm^{-1} may have some contribution from $\text{Pd}\leftarrow\text{N}$ vibration. The M—N vibration in $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes of HASETU is reported to occur as a medium intensity band in the region $505\text{--}526\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ⁵. On this basis it may be appropriate to consider the band at 510 cm^{-1} in the palladium complex as due to $\text{Pd}\leftarrow\text{N}$ vibration. It is worthwhile to state that Condrate and Nakamoto⁸ have attributed the band at 550 cm^{-1} to the Pd-nitrogen stretching vibration in *trans*-bis-(glycino) Pd(II). Watt and Klett⁹ have assigned bands in the region $500\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to metal-nitrogen stretching modes in the chelated ethylenediamine complexes of Pd (II) and Pt (II) halides.

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The results of present investigation are consistent with the formulation of the palladium complex as,

in which HASETU acts as a neutral bidentate ligand. Other formulations are, however, not completely excluded.

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